

Numerical Modelling of Potential Volcanic Landslide Tsunami at the Anak Krakatau Island (Indonesia) – A Circular Collapse Case Study

MA Sarker

Technical Director, Royal Haskoning DHV, Rightwell House, Bretton, Peterborough PE3 8DW, United Kingdom.
E-mail: zaman.sarker@rhdhv.com

ABSTRACT

The Krakatau Island volcano in Indonesia erupted on 22nd December 2018 which caused the collapse of the south-western flank of the Anak Krakatau Island triggering a tsunami. However, there are still chances for collapse of the other sides (flanks) of Anak Krakatau Island in future. Therefore, tsunami from a circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island has been numerically modelled in this study to cover any potential future collapse of any side of the island. The initial tsunami waves similar to the 22nd December 2018 event have been generated based on previous studies found in the literature search. The MIKE21 Flow Model FM of DHI has been used in this study to simulate the tsunami. Sample results from the tsunami modelling study are presented in this paper for illustration purposes. The methodology described in this paper for modelling the volcanic tsunami at Anak Krakatau Island could also be applied to simulate this type of events at other sites around the world.

Key words: Tsunami, Volcano, Natural Hazards, Anak Krakatau, Krakatau Island, Bay of Bengal, Numerical Modelling, Port Development, RHDHV

1. INTRODUCTION

The volcanic eruption on 22nd December 2018 caused the collapse of the south-western flank of the Anak Krakatau Island triggering a tsunami. However, there are still chances for collapse of the other sides (flanks) of the Anak Krakatau Island in future. Therefore, tsunami from a circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island has been numerically modelled in this study to cover any potential future collapse of any side of the island.

The MIKE21 Flow Model FM of DHI [1] has been used in the study. The initial tsunami conditions (changes in sea surface) similar to the 22nd December 2018 event were generated in the study that matched the findings of other authors. Initially numerical modelling of the 22nd December 2018 was carried out as described in [2] to validate the tsunami model. Then the validated model was used to simulate the tsunami generated from the circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island in the present study. Sample results of tsunami levels and arrival time from the modelling study are presented in this paper for illustration purposes only.

The model could be used to simulate the passage of a tsunami anywhere within the Bay of Bengal and its surroundings including Indonesia. The methodology described in this paper for modelling the tsunami generated at the Anak Krakatau Island in the Sunda Strait could also be applied to simulate this type of events at other sites around the world. The flowchart in Figure 1 [adapted from (3)] illustrates the steps and the software used in the present study.

Regional Tidal Model Set Up by Royal HaskoningDHV

Royal HaskoningDHV has set up a two-dimensional Regional Tidal Hydrodynamic Model for the Bay of Bengal and its surroundings using the MIKE21 Flow Model FM software of DHI [1].

The regional model covers the coastlines of six countries – India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Malaysia and Indonesia (see Figure 3). The model bathymetry (as shown in Figure 3) was obtained from the C-Map Global Database [5]. This regional tidal model was used in the study to simulate the tsunami propagation.

Fig. 1 Steps and software used in the tsunami modelling study [adapted from (3)]

The general definition of tsunami level and wave height is illustrated in Figure 2[4].

Fig. 2 General definition of tsunami level and tsunami wave height [4]

Model Mesh and Bathymetry

A flexible (triangular) mesh was used with variable mesh size distribution to obtain accuracy in the model results. Attention was given to the shallow areas and inside the Sunda Strait particularly around the Krakatau Island. Typically, 20-30 grids (ideally 40 grids) per wavelength are required to correctly resolve the physical processes of tsunami propagation. Shallower waters have shorter wavelengths. Therefore, smaller grid sizes are required for shallower waters.

The mesh size distribution was generally as below:

- 50m grid size at 1m depth
- 150m grid size at 10m depth
- 500m grid size at 100m depth
- 1500m grid size at 1000m depth
- 3000m grid size for the remaining deeper areas

The bathymetry of the model domain was obtained from the C-Map Database [5]. Figure 3 shows the model domain and bathymetry.

Fig. 3 The regional model domain and bathymetry [with zoomed-in views]

Model Parameters

Some other major model parameters are given below:

- Minimum time step = 0.01s
- Maximum time step = 15s
- Critical Courant-Friedrich-Lévy (CFL) number = 0.8
- Run duration = 3 hours
- Higher order numerical scheme used
- Coriolis force = varying in domain

Initial Tsunami Levels

The generation of the initial tsunami levels from the 22nd December 2018 event has been described in [2]. The parameters and approach used in [2] for the south-western slide were also used to generate the initial tsunami levels from the circular collapse. The initial tsunami condition used in the [2] study was at the time when the tsunami wave had developed (i.e. ~50 seconds to 1 minute after the event) for input to the hydrostatic model. The initial tsunami wave length was approximately 2.2km and the initial tsunami wave period was approximately 63s in view of the hydrostatic modelling approach used in the [2] study. The initial tsunami wave level was approximately 75m. Figure 4 shows the initial tsunami levels used in the present study from the circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island.

Fig. 4 Initial tsunami levels (potential circular collapse)

Fig. 5 Selected output locations [Image source – Google Earth]

Model Calibration

The modelled peak tsunami levels and arrival time from the 22nd December 2018 event were extracted at selected locations. These locations are shown in Figure 5.

Observed tsunami level at Carita during the 22nd December 2018 event was obtained from [6] as reported in [7]. Observed tsunami level and arrival time at Marina Jumbo were obtained from [8]. The modelled tsunami levels and arrival time are compared in Table 1 with the observed values where available.

Table -1 Modelled and observed tsunami levels and arrival time from the 22nd December 2018 event

Ciwandan Port (6.016°S, 105.954°E)		Marina Jumbo (6.19°S, 105.82°E)		Carita (6.263°S, 105.8°E)	
Modelled Tsunami	Observed Tsunami	Modelled Tsunami	Observed Tsunami	Modelled Tsunami	Observed Tsunami
0.7 to 1.6m (51 minutes)	- (50 minutes)	0.8 to 1.3m (36 minutes)	0.9m (29 minutes)	1.4-2.2m (34 minutes)	2.0m -

A good agreement was found both in the modelled and observed tsunami levels and arrival time at various locations within the Sunda Strait. Therefore, it is concluded that the present model can predict the tsunami levels and arrival time anywhere within the model domain with an acceptable level of confidence for the circular collapse scenario.

Model Results and Discussion

Propagation of tsunami waves over time is shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows the time-series of tsunami levels at selected locations. These locations were shown in Figure 5. Figure 8 illustrates the maximum tsunami levels during the entire passage of the tsunami. Peak tsunami levels and its arrival time are summarized in Table 2.

The maximum tsunami level at the Anak Krakatau Island was 92m. The maximum tsunami level at the Sertung Island was 38.6m. The maximum tsunami level at the Krakatau Island was 26.3m. The maximum tsunami level at the Krakatau Kitjil was 11.8m. The maximum tsunami level at Sebisi Island was 7.7m at its southern coastline whereas the maximum tsunami level at the Sebuku Island was 2.8m at its western coastline. A tsunami level of up to 3.5m was found at the Sangiang Island at its western coastline. A tsunami level of up to 3.8m was found at the eastern coastline of the Panaitan Island. Up to 0.9m tsunami level was found at the eastern coastline of the Sawangbalak Island. The maximum tsunami level at Legundi Island was 1.8m whereas the maximum tsunami level at the Siuntjal Island was 1.3m. The maximum tsunami levels in the Java Sea and the Indian Ocean were relatively small (0.4m and 0.2m respectively).

The model results suggest that the neighbouring islands (Sertung Island, Krakatau Kitjil Island and Krakatau Island) were quickly affected (within 2 minutes) due to the proximity to the source. The Sebisi Island, Legundi Island and Siuntjal Island (all situated north of the source) were also affected relatively quickly (within 25 minutes). The Sawangbalak Island at north-east was affected within 23 minutes. The Panaitan Island at south-west was affected within 30 minutes. The Sebuku Island at north-east was affected within 28 minutes. The tsunami took 38 minutes to reach the Sangiang Island situated north-east of the source. The tsunami took about one hour to reach the Java Sea at north-east whereas it took only about half an hour to reach the Indian Ocean at south-west.

The model correctly reproduced the tsunami phenomena observed on site with the sea level rising and receding leaving a drying beach and foreshore followed by a rapid rise in the level of the sea. The nearby islands, headlands and coastlines were worst affected due to its proximity. The highest level of 92m was found at south-west coast of Anak Krakatau Island immediately after the event.

A relatively higher rise in sea surface elevation was found in the shallower water depths. Rise in water level at shallow waters is higher than that in deeper waters as expected due to shoaling effects.

(a) Tsunami levels at t = 0 minutes

(b) Tsunami levels at t = 5 minutes

(c) Tsunami levels at t = 10minutes

(d) Tsunami levels at t = 15 minutes

(e) Tsunami levels at t = 20 minutes

(f) Tsunami levels at t = 30 minutes

(g) Tsunami levels at t = 45 minutes

(h) Tsunami levels at t = 1 hour

(i) Tsunami levels at t = 1 hour 30 minutes

(j) Tsunami levels at t = 2 hours

Fig. 6 Propagation of tsunami waves

Fig. 7 Time-series of tsunami levels at selected locations

Fig. 8 Maximum tsunami levels (with zoomed-in views)

Table -2 Peak tsunami levels and its arrival time at selected locations

Locations	Position with respect to the source	Peak tsunami levels (+mMSL)	Arrival time of peak tsunami levels (minutes)
Anak Krakatau Island	Source	92.0	0
Sertung Island	West	38.6	1
Krakatau Island	South-east	26.3	2
Krakatau Kitjil Island	East	11.8	2
Sebesi Island	North-east	7.7	17
Sebuku Island	North-east	2.8	51 (28*)
Sangiang Island	North-east	3.5	38
Legundi Island	North-west	1.8	24
Sawangbalak Island	North-west	0.9	23
Panaitan Island	South-west	3.8	30
Siuntjal Island	North-west	1.3	25
Java Sea	North-east	0.4	95 (59*)
Indian Ocean	South-west	0.2	140 (28*)

* arrival time of the first wave which is smaller than the peak wave

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Numerical modelling of tsunami generated by potential future circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island was carried out in this study. This paper illustrates how a tidal hydrodynamic model can be used to simulate the impacts of a tsunami on coastal developments, facilities and communities.

Findings from the tsunami modelling study are summarised below:

- a) The maximum tsunami level of about 92m was found at the south-western coastline of the Anak Krakatau Island.
- b) The other three neighbouring islands (Sertung Island, Krakatau Island and Krakatau Kitjil Island) were affected the most due to their proximity.
- c) The maximum tsunami level at the nearest island (Sertung Island) was 38.6m and it took only one minute for the tsunami to reach its eastern coastline.
- d) The maximum tsunami level at the nearby Krakatau Island was 26.3m and it took only two minutes for the tsunami to reach its north-eastern coastline.
- e) The maximum tsunami level at the nearby Krakatau Kitjil Island was 11.8m and it took only two minutes for the tsunami to reach its western coastline.
- f) The maximum tsunami level at the Sebisi Island was 7.7m and it took 17 minutes for the tsunami to reach its southern coastline.
- g) The maximum tsunami level at the Sebuku Island was 2.8m and it took 28 minutes for the first tsunami wave to reach its south-western coastline.
- h) The maximum tsunami level at the Panaitan Island was 3.8m and it took 30 minutes for the tsunami to reach its north-western coastline.
- i) The maximum tsunami level at the Sangiang Island was 3.5m and it took 38 minutes for the tsunami to reach its north-western coastline.
- j) The maximum tsunami level at the Legundi Island was 1.8m and it took 24 minutes for the tsunami to reach its north-western coastline.
- k) The maximum tsunami level at the Sawangbalak Island was 0.9m and it took 23 minutes for the tsunami to reach its eastern coastline.
- l) The maximum tsunami level at the Siuntjal Island was 1.3m and it took 25 minutes for the tsunami to reach its north-western coastline.
- m) The maximum tsunami level in the Java Sea was 0.4m and it took about an hour for the first tsunami wave to reach there.
- n) The maximum tsunami level in the Indian Ocean was 0.2m and it took about half an hour for the first tsunami wave to reach there.

The methodology described in this paper for numerical modelling of tsunami generated by potential future circular collapse of the Anak Krakatau Island in the Sunda Strait of Indonesia could also be applied to simulate this type of events at other sites around the world.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Royal HaskoningDHV (an independent, international engineering and project management consultancy company, www.royalhaskoningdhv.com) for giving permission to publish this paper. The author would also like to thank the external reviewer(s) who provided valuable comments to improve the paper.

REFERENCES

- [1]. DHI (2020a). MIKE21 Flow Model FM User Guide, DK-2970, Hørsholm, Denmark, 2019.
- [2]. Sarker, M. A. (2020). Numerical Modelling of the 22nd December 2018 Volcanic Landslide Tsunami at the Anak Krakatau Island (Indonesia). *European Journal of Advances in Engineering and Technology*, 2020, Volume 7, Issue 5, pages 42-56.
- [3]. Sarker, M. A. (2018). Numerical Modelling of Tsunami in the Makran Subduction Zone –A Case Study on the 1945 Event. *Journal of Operational Oceanography*, Published by Taylor & Francis, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1755876X.2018.1527883>.
- [4]. Sarker, M. A. (2019). Numerical Modelling of the 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami by Royal HaskoningDHV. *International Journal of Innovative Studies in Sciences and Engineering Technology (IJISSET)*, Volume 5, Issue 7, <http://ijisсет.org/articles/2019-2/volume-5-issue-7/>.
- [5]. C-Map (2014). JEPPESEN Commercial Marine, Hovlandsveien 52, Egersund, Postal Code 4370, Norway, 2014, available online at <http://www.jepesen.com/index.jsp>.
- [6]. *Mediastara, Yulida (2018)*. "BNPB Terima Informasi Tinggi Tsunami Selat Sunda 2-5 Meter". *Detik (in Indonesian)*. Dated 25 December 2018, retrieved 12 January 2019.
- [7]. Wikipedia (2020c). 2018 Sunda Strait tsunami. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Sunda_Strait_tsunami#cite_note-21.

- [8]. JRC-EU (2018). Indonesia - Volcanic Eruption & Tsunami GLIDE: TS-2018-000423-IDN GDACS Volcano RED Alert. JRC Emergency Reporting - Activation #029 - 24 Dec 2018.